

Original Article

HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES AS DRIVERS OF COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN RIVERS SOUTH-WEST, RIVERS STATE

Worlu Precious Nkem and Johnson Oghenekaro Blessing

Department of Adult and Community Education,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17161348>

Abstract: This study examined the influence of human resource development (HRD) programmes on community development in Rivers South-West Senatorial District, Rivers State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, targeting a population of 1,560, from which a sample of 468 respondents was selected using proportionate random sampling. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire validated by three experts and tested for reliability using the test-retest method, yielding a coefficient r-value of 0.78. Research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while hypotheses were tested with t-tests at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that computer and rural agricultural management skill development programmes had a greater positive influence on female respondents compared to their male counterparts in promoting community development. Based on these findings, the study recommends increased awareness and publication of programme benefits, particularly targeting male participation. Additionally, training centres should be established closer to communities, and programme objectives should be aligned with the specific needs and challenges of beneficiaries to maximize their impact on community development within the senatorial district and the state at large.

Keywords: Human Resource Development, Programmes, Community Development, Skills Training, Rivers State

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Rivers South West Senatorial District is made up of seven sub-districts namely; Ahoada West, Ahoada East, Abua-Odual, Ogba-Egbema Ndoni, Akuku-Toru, Asari-Toru and Degema, it is situated along the Niger Delta region of the Southern part of Nigeria, Rivers south-west stand as the major economic strength of this great nation (Nigeria) through her rich in mineral (oil and gas)institutions, agriculture and other numerous economic activities which made it more attractive and hospitable for investors and tourist.

The districts despite this wealth as described above is characterised by poverty, knapping insecurity, illiteracy, high rate of mother/child mortality, hunger and killings. Though lot of effort have being made over the years by government, non-government, private and cooperate organisations so as to tackle these problems through programmes (ies) in order to solve the problems andalso breach the gaps between the poor and the rich, illiterates and literates in boosting their socio-economic strength in order to solve the root of these problems in providing a

Original Article

peaceful and healthy living. The training programmes were introduced to help the rural people develop themselves and also fit into the society/system and then develop their various communities. It is hard to believe that a region so blessed and rich can be characterised by such ugly scenario, this is the reason while programmes like: The adolescent project (TAP) a non-governmental organisation project, Young women economic empowerment (YWEEP) Information communication skill programmes, Rural agricultural skill programmes, health awareness programmes, women and the girl child empowerment/skill acquisition programmes, skill acquisition on computer and conflict resolution programme etc were organised to empower and better the lives of the people in this seven sub-districts. Despite these efforts the manpower needed to improve the area was still inadequate while because the aim was not on man which also shows in the level of development in these communities. An interview carried out during a visit to this area to discover the reason for the slow and lack of development, increase in social violence and other criminal activities attest that there is no solid developmental plan for the manpower needed to effect the required changes in these districts. It is true that some training programmes have been introduced over time as a way to empower or build the human capacity that will enable them be useful to themselves and fit into the society/system and develop their various communities economically. The outcome of it all was not much felt due to neglect in tackling the challenges, problems, needs from the root; more so the characteristics of the beneficiaries or trainees were not considered and even after the completion of each of these programmes as earlier stated the needed financial support for as start-up support was not given as a result the skill and knowledge gained and acquired wasn't utilized which rendered the socio-economic development goal and objective the programmes null and unachievable, resulting what the districts is suffering today which militated this study as a way of providing a lasting solution to this problems because if the people were adequately carried a long in the plan before and after the training programmes, they will be able to use the knowledge and skill acquired effectively to better themselves, develop their community and also end the menace that has not only kept them dormant and poor but also threaten the peace of the people.

Community in whatever form consist of people (men women and the youth) with peculiar challenges, needs and interest and its problem which is seeing as a problem for all, that is the reason why its problems is being reflected in the larger community (the local government, state and the nation) today. The disparities between its natural endowments, its contribution to national growth and the level of its manpower is so large which is the more reason why this districts are so back-ward in meeting its needs or in solving her day to day challenges. This situation called for an urgent intervention from government, non-governmental organisations and private bodies in bringing an end to this ugly menace. human resources development programmes has become an essential tools in equipping both male and female in arresting and correcting this ugly menace in a very responsible/possible way in a short period of time. Human resources development programmes are programmes carried out outside the formal system of learning, desired to meet both immediate and future need of every beneficiaries that is the more reason while it remains the best solution to problems. This is while Michael, Marquardt and Mtahoutshi (2013) sees it as that type of programme which enhances or empowers and educate individuals, groups, organisation, communities, nation and ultimately bring about the expected change in the individual. Looking at the 2010 index report of human development from United Nation Development Programme (UNDP), Nigeria as a country was listed as one of the 'E9' level, meaning that Nigeria fall within the 9 countries rated with the high

Original Article

number of illiterates due to high rate of poverty. This does not only affirm the level of poverty but poverty of human capital development. What had sustained and accentuated the poverty level in Nigeria among others is lack of basic skills and capacity for productive ventures, it is a fact that the strength, wealth and level of development of any family, community, state or nation depends entirely on man (human capacity) thus the helpless situations facing this district and the nation today.

The solution to the above problem can only be solved/tackled by man as the active agent that is able to exploit and accumulates both wealth and material resources, builds solid socio-economic and political organisation have the ability to manipulates on the resources and national possessions which are lifeless factors of production thereby in enhancing community and national development as well. (Okoye and Ezejiofor 2013)

Development whether in man, organisation or community before the early 1970s, according to Michael (2011) seems to be focused on the economic benefits or profits an individual or a country records. But with time due to changes that took place in so many areas/works of life, development became something more than economic development, rather economy was viewed as a part of development. Community development is much more than infrastructural development, correctly it cuts a cross every areaof live, whether in innovation, correction of error, utilization of the natural resources, job delivery and in goal achievement. Community development as an issue has become a social concern. This is because the root course of poverty, mother/child mortality, health issues, illiteracy, teenage pregnancy, early marriage, inefficiency and low productivity, crimes, stealing or robbery, killings and knapping can only be tackle from the community level.

Without the development of man in any societies around the world, the degradation of natural resources will continue, as more humans are not offered the knowledge and skills necessary for them to become productive constituents and contributors to world progress.

Diverse communities and organizations need individuals capable of operating effectively in diverse cultural environment using increasing complex organizational structures and communication patterns in managing changes using multiple integrative business strategies with an embedded global perspective. Sustainable development is possible only when human beings are properly educated and trained to meet the needs and challenges of their society. Proving that human resources development is the major component of sustainable development (Saunier, 2000).

The society is a social-system due to its interaction with man in his/her environment. The need for making profit or achieving desired goal/output or doing what is needed to be done at a particular point in time cannot be over emphasized. Until attention is diverted from material resources to man (human being) as the only necessary tool or instrument for actualizing our dream as a people and nation, then can we get it done. Looking at the system whether social, political, economic, or institutional; things seem not having the expected result or output that can either take the individual, organization and society to the desired level or meet expected target which is the reason for Human Resources Development.

The main concept of community development is basically captured in two major words - "Community" and "Development". Frankenberg in Onyeozu (2007) sees community as a territory bounded by social system within which people live, sharing common social economic and cultural characteristics. Often, whenever the issue of community is being mention; what comes into mind is the village settlement. The difficulty in providing a

Original Article

definition of community that should be sufficient for all purpose and people is due to its flexibility. The term community entails the interaction of several elements whose geographical boundaries are a clear function of time, place and context of issue under consideration. (Osuji,1991). There is general consensus today that the purpose of development besides enhancing income generation goes along with broadening the choices of the with respect to decent education, good health, political freedom, cultural identity, personal security, and many other areas of human wellbeing. The term human resource development refers to the process of increasing knowledge, skills and capabilities of all the people in the society through formal education, job trainings, adult education programmes, self-development programmes and through institutionalized ways.

In recognition of the importance of human capital development, the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (1991) has described human resources as the knowledge, skills, attitudes, physical and managerial effort required to manipulate capital, technology, land and material to produce goods and services for human consumption. In the same vein, Mahroum (2007) suggested that at the macro-level, human capital management is about three key capacities namely; the capacity to develop talent, the capacity to deploy talent, and the capacity to draw talent from elsewhere. Collectively, these three capacities formed the backbone of any country's human capital competitiveness in a corroborative view. Simkovic (2013) affirms that the only means of success in business today is through manpower development. So developing human capital requires creating and cultivating environment in which human beings can rapidly learn and apply new ideas, competencies, skills, behaviours and attitudes. It could therefore, be deduced that human capital represents the stock of competencies, knowledge, habits, social and personality attributes, including creativity, cognitive abilities, embodied in the ability to perform labour so as to produce economic value.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of human resource development programmes on community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District. The study sought to:

1. To determine the extent computer skills development programme will influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state?
2. To examine the extent conflict resolution management skills development programme will influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state?
3. To investigate the extent rural agricultural skills development programme will influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state?
4. To identify the extent inter personal treatment skills development programme will influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state?

1.4 Research Questions:

The following questions were designed to guide the study;

1. To what extent does computer skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.
2. To what extent does conflict resolution management skills development influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

Original Article

3. To what extent does rural agricultural skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

4. To what extent does interpersonal treatment skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of computer skills programme in community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

2 There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of conflict resolution management skills programme in community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

3 There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of rural agricultural skills programme in community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

4 There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of inter personal treatment skills programme in community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the researcher used various methods and techniques in the analysis of this study which includes Research design, population of the study sample and sampling techniques, instrumentation, validity of the study, reliability of the instrument, administration of the instrument, data analysis procedure.

3.1 Research Design

The researcher adopted the descriptive survey research design in this study because the research is on the impact of human resources development programme on community development in Rivers South-West Senatorial District of Rivers State. Survey design is used to ascertain the current status of the problem or phenomenon by studying a true representative of the population. Thus, the design handles situational problems and suggests solution to them.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of 1560 beneficiaries of the types of human resources developments programme in Rivers West Senatorial Districts of Rivers State

Table 3.1 Population of Beneficiaries of Human Resources Development Programme in Rivers West Senatorial districts.

S/No	Local Government Area	Population of Beneficiaries
1	Ahoada West LGA	260
2	Ahoada East LGA	220
3	AbuaOdual LGA	130
4	Ogba – Egbema Ndoni LGA	220

Original Article

5	Akuku-Toru LGA	330
6	Degema LGA	240
7.	Asari-Toru LGA	160
Total		1560

Source: Rivers State Ministry of Rural Development (Report 2017)

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

The sample size was four hundred and sixty eight (468) which was 30% of the total population of the beneficiaries of human resources development and sampling technique used in the study was proportionate random sampling technique to select 30% of the total population which was Four hundred sixty eight (468) made up of 300 male and 168 female of the selected beneficiaries of the types of human resources developments programme in Rivers West Senatorial Districts of Rivers State.

3.4 Instrument for Data Collection

The research instruments for this study was structured questionnaire constructed by the researcher, the questions were structured with simple sentences on the extend each of these programmes have influenced the beneficiaries on community development. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents after explaining to the respondents their roles and purpose of the study with the help of four research assistance for adequate distribution and effective coverage based on the programmes on area such: computer skill development programme (CSDP), conflict resolution management skills development programme scale (CRMSDP), rural agricultural skills development programme(RASDP) and interpersonal treatment skills programme development (ITSDP)the first instrument is divided into two parts, Section A which deals with personal data while B to E contains four groups in different sections of the various programmes as established in chapter 1.

3.5 Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was given to my supervisor and two experts in the field of human resources development and community development for validation. Their comments and contributions were used to improve on the quality of the instrument in terms of facts and contents validity, sentence structure and relevance.

3.6 Reliability of Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established using test-retest reliability method. The instrument was administered twice to a group of 20 persons elected in the study area but not of the study group at two weeks interval. The responses were correlated using Pearson product moment correlations coefficient (PPMCC). A reliability coefficient index (r) of 0.78 was obtained.

3.7 Administration of the Instrument

The researcher personally administered the instrument with two other trained research assistants with the purpose of facilitating good responses and adequate coverage of the research areas. Four hundred and sixty-eight questionnaires were administered to respondents which completed and retrieved within an interval of two weeks.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The questionnaire was structured on a four (4) point modified Likert type scale.

Original Article

Very High Extent (VHE = 4 point), High Extent (HE= 3 point) representing positive responses. While Low Extent (LE = 2 point) and Very Low Extent (VLE = 1 point) represents negative responses. More over for each question, mean (x) and percentage was used to analyse the responses. Decision points or criterion mean is 2.5

Thus; criterion means Summation of Weight Number of Items

$$4+3+2+1/4 = 2.50$$

Any mean below 2.50 (criteria means) was rejected and all mean equal to or above 2.50 was accepted.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section deals with the presentation of analyzed data. The analyzed data and results of the study are systematically presented with respect to the four (4) research questions, four (4) formulated null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule is that where the calculated mean is less than the criteria mean (2.50), the responses were not accepted (rejected) but where the calculated mean is equal or greater than the criteria mean, it was accepted. M (Mean), SD (Standard Deviation), RMK (Remark)

Research Question 1: To what extent does computer skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state?

Table 4.1: Mean response: Computer skill development programme and community development

Female (N = 168) Male (N = 300)

S/N	Items	M	S.D	RMK	M	S.D	RMK
1	I can operate computer system	3.08	0.96	HE	1.98	0.98	LE
2	I have gained an employment due to my knowledge in computer skill	3.12	0.99	HE	1.94	0.97	LE
3	I am training other youth in computer training skill programme in my community	3.00	1.00	HE	2.03	1.02	LE
4	The knowledge I acquired helped in gaining an admission in to the university	3.07	0.95	HE	1.97	1.00	LE
5	I was up-graded due to proficient in the use of micro software	2.02	1.08	LE	2.10	1.00	LE
	Grand mean	2.86	1.00	HE	2.01	0.99	LE

Original Article

Field Data 2017:

Table 4.1 shows the results on the extent computer skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. As shown in the table, grand mean value of 2.86 for female respondents indicates that they perceived that computer skill development programme influence community development to a high extent. A grand mean value of 2.01 for the male respondents however indicates that they perceived that computer skill development programme influence community development to a low extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does conflict resolution management skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state.

Table 4.2: Mean response: Conflict resolution management skill programme and community development

		Female (N = 168)			Male (N = 300)		
S/N	Items	M	S.D	RMK	M	S.D	RMK
1	It help our community in disaster and abandonment of activities in the calming the angry youth during crises	2.07	0.98	LE	2.01	1.02	LE
2	Peace has restore peace to the Rivers West Senatorial Districts	2.05	0.96	LE	1.98	0.98	LE
3	It has enable reconciliation among grieved families	2.05	1.05	LE	1.95	0.96	LE
4	Normal activities has returned to my community after many months of community	1.92	0.90	LE	1.98	0.98	LE
Grand mean		2.02	0.97	LE	1.98	0.99	LE

Field data: 2017

Table 4.2 shows the results on the extent conflict resolution management skills influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. As shown in the table, grand mean value of 2.02 for female respondents indicates that they perceived that conflict resolution management skills influence community development to a low extent. A grand mean value of 1.98 for the male respondents also indicates that they perceived that conflict resolution management skills influence community development to a low extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does rural agricultural skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state?

Original Article

Table 4.3: Mean response: Rural agricultural skills programme and community development

S/N	Items	Female (N = 168)			Male (N = 300)		
		M	S.D	RMK	M	S.D	RMK
1	I can grow difference crops with a short period of time in a small portion of land	3.04	1.03	HE	2.12	1.03	LE
2	I am conscientious about good record keeping of my profits, yield and losses for assessments purposes	2.92	0.93	HE	1.99	1.04	LE
3	I understand the importance of the use of fertilizer and its benefits to me as a farmer	3.05	1.00	HE	1.98	0.99	LE
4	The training has exposed me and my fellow farmers to varieties of crops and skills in the field of agriculture in my community	2.96	1.01	HE	1.93	0.96	LE
5	I hudge harvest due to the use of improve varieties	3.04	1.01	HE	1.98	1.00	LE
6	The skill I acquired have improved my socioeconomic status of my family and community	2.99	1.02	HE	2.05	0.98	LE
Grand mean		3.00	1.00	HE	2.01	1.00	LE

Field data: 2017

Table 4.3 shows the results on the extent rural agricultural skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. As shown in the table, grand mean value of 3.00 for female respondents indicates that they perceived that rural agricultural skills development programme influence community development to a high extent. A grand mean value of 2.01 for the male respondents also indicates that they perceived that rural agricultural skills development programme influence community development to a low extent.

Research Question 4: To what extent does interpersonal treatment skills development programme influence community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state.

Original Article

Table 4.4: Mean response: Interpersonal treatment skill programme and community development

sS/N Items	Female (N = 168)			Male (N = 300)		
	M	S.D	RMK	M	S.D	RMK
1 Health workers can now listen to us very well	3.08	0.93	HE	2.99	1.01	HE
2 I no longer depend on traditional medicine	3.07	0.96	HE	3.06	0.99	HE
3 I am no longer ashamed of telling the health worker everything about my health challenges	3.01	1.01	HE	3.01	1.02	HE
4 I am not scared of my vaccine	2.95	1.08	HE	3.00	0.96	HE
5 I can conveniently go on medical check-up on regular bases	2.89	1.08	HE	3.00	0.97	HE
6 Due to information I acquired during the training programme I now understand the importance of hygiene practices to healthy living	3.02	0.98	HE	3.04	1.00	HE
Grand mean	3.00	1.01	HE	3.02	0.99	HE

Field data: 2017

Table 4.4 shows the results on the extent interpersonal treatment skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. As shown in the table, grand mean value of 3.00 for female respondents indicates that they perceived that interpersonal treatment skills development programme influence community development to a high extent. A grand mean value of 3.02 for the male respondents also indicates that they perceived that interpersonal treatment skills development programme influence community development to a high extent.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of computer skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state.

Table 4.5: Analysis of male and female responses on the influence of computer programme On community development.

Groups	N	M	S.D	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Female	168	2.86	0.46				

Original Article

466 15.53 1.97 Rejected Male 300 2.01 0.62

Field data: 2017

Table 4.5 shows the result of the t-test for difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents regarding the influence of computer skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result shows that calculated value of t (t-cal, degree of freedom of 466) = 15.53 is higher than critical value of t (tcrit, degree of freedom of 466) = 1.97. Based on this, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean response of male and female respondents regarding the influence of computer skills development programme in community development, meaning that the female folks enrolled more and also have employment opportunity as it seeing in the business centres around us.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of conflict resolution management skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state.

Table 4.6: T-test Analysis of male and female responses on the influence of conflict resolution on community development.

Groups	N	M	S.D	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Female	168	2.02	0.67				
466	0.64	1.97	Accepted	Male	300	1.98	0.65

Field data: 2017

Table 4.6 shows the result of the t-test for difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents regarding the influence of conflict resolution management skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result shows that calculated value of t (t-cal, degree of freedom of 466) = 0.64 is less than critical value of t (t-crit, degree of freedom of 466) = 1.97. Based on this, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there was no significant difference in the mean response of male and female respondents regarding the influence of conflict resolution management skills development programme on community development.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of rural agricultural skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state.

Table 4.7: T-test Analysis of male and female responses on the influence of agricultural skills on community development.

Groups	N	M	S.D	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Female	168	3.00	0.61				
466	17.20	1.97	Reject	Male	300	2.01	0.59

Original Article

Field data: 2017

Table: 4.7 shows the result of the t-test for difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents regarding the influence of rural agricultural skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result shows that calculated value of t (t-cal, degree of freedom of 466) = 17.20 is higher than critical value of t (t-crit, degree of freedom of 466) = 1.97. Based on this, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean response of male and female respondents regarding the influence of rural agricultural skills development programme on community development.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents on the influence of interpersonal treatment skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state

Table 4.8: T-test Analysis of male and female responses on the influence of interpersonal treatment skills programme on community development.

Groups	N	M	S.D	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Female	168	3.00	0.63				
466	-0.22	1.97	Reject	Male	300	3.02	0.59

Field data 2017

Table: 4.8 shows the result of the t-test for difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents regarding the influence of interpersonal treatment skills development programme on community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result shows that calculated value of t (t-cal, degree of freedom of 466) = 0.22 is less than critical value of t (tcrit, degree of freedom of 466) = 1.97. Based on this, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean response of male and female respondents regarding the influence of interpersonal treatment skills development programme on community development.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The sections present discussions of the findings of this study. Findings are discussed based on the findings to each research questions and the corresponding hypothesis.

4.3.1 Computer Skills Development Programme and Community Development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers State

Research question 1, sought to find out the extent computer skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result from the analysis reveals that the female beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme agree that: they can operate computer; they gained employment through computer knowledge; they were also training others in computer knowledge; computer knowledge they acquired help them in gaining admission to a high extent. They however responded that the extent computer skill aided their up-grade in work place was low. On the other hand, the male beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme disagree that they can operate computer; they gained employment through computer knowledge; they were training others in computer knowledge; computer

Original Article

knowledge they acquired help them in gaining admission; computer skill aided their up-grade in work place. Generally, the result shows that the influence of computer skill development programme on community development was higher for the female beneficiaries than for the male beneficiaries. This higher influence for the female than for the male beneficiaries may have been caused by the fact that the female beneficiaries had higher level of participation and commitment to the programme than their male counterparts. Sequel to this, they might have secured small job opportunities or set up small business centres after training. More so it is commonly known that most small business centres where they carry out photocopies and typesetting jobs are being operated by female folks. This could have motivated the female beneficiaries to be very committed in course of the training and hence the result so obtained. The result of hypothesis shows that there was a significant difference in the mean response of the female and male beneficiaries of the human development programme regarding the influence of computer skill development programme on community development; with the programme having more influence on community development for the female than for their male counterparts.

As stated above, computer skill development programme highly influenced female beneficiaries in terms of community development. This negates the findings of Kobani (2014) who conducted a study to examine the impact of empowerment programmes on women participation in community development in six local government areas of Rivers state. Kobani found out that the empowerment support initiatives had low influence on women's participation in community development in Rivers State. On the other hand, Kobani's finding corroborates the findings for the male beneficiaries of computer skill development programme since it was found in the present study that computer skill development programme lowly influenced male beneficiaries in terms of community development.

4.3.2 Conflict Resolution Management Skills Development Programme and Community Development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Research question 2, sought to find out the extent conflict resolution management skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result from the analysis reveals that both the female and male beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme agree that the programme: helped them in propounding solution to the youth recklessness their communities; brought about peace in their communities; made possible the reconciliation between a grieved families; resulted in normal activities in their communities to a low extent. This result could be evident by the fact that despites much effort by various bodies to intervene in the crisis in this study area, killings, armed robbery, kidnapping and other forms of vices are still being experienced.

The result of hypothesis two shows that there was no significant difference in the mean response of the female and male beneficiaries of the human development programme regarding the influence conflict resolution management skills development programme on community development. This implies that both male and female beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme agree that the programmeresulted in normal activities in their communities to a low extent.

This result confirms the finding of Olori, Dimkpa and Olori (2015) who conducted a study to examine the extent community education has contributed to the eradication of poverty among communities in Rivers State of Nigeria.

Original Article

One of the findings was that the community education contributed very lowly to the reduction in security treat in the study area.

4.3.3 Rural Agricultural Skills Development Programme and Community Development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Research question three sought to find out the extent rural agricultural skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result from the analysis reveals that the female beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme agree that based on the training: they grow different types of crops; they were conscientious about good record keeping; understood the importance of the use of fertilizer and its benefits to a farmer; they were exposed to varieties of crops and skills in the field of agriculture; have huge harvest; the socio-economic status of their family and community has improved to a high extent.

On the other hand, the male beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme responded that they could grow different types of crops; they were conscientious about good record keeping; understood the importance of the use of fertilizer and its benefits to a farmer; they were exposed to varieties of crops and skills in the field of agriculture; they know how to preserve my farm products; the socio-economic status of their family and community has improved to a low extent. Generally, the result shows that the influence of rural agricultural skills development programme on community development was higher for the female beneficiaries than for the male beneficiaries.

The result of hypothesis 3 shows that there was a significant difference in the mean response of the female and male beneficiaries of the human development programme regarding the influence of rural agricultural skills development programme on community development; with the programme having more influence on community development for the female than for their male counterparts. This higher influence for the female than for the male beneficiaries may have been caused by the fact that the female beneficiaries had higher level of participated and commitment to the programme than their male counterparts. Experience shows that the female are more into farming activities than the male. Sequel to this, the female beneficiaries may have shown higher level of participation and commitment to the programme knowing that it could help them in their farming activities so as to meet up with their family needs. The male beneficiaries may have thought that the agricultural skill programme is more of a woman's thing and as such may have not been very committed.

As stated above, agricultural skills development programme highly influenced female beneficiaries in terms of community development. This corroborates the findings of Ikegwu, Ajiboye, Aromolaran, Ayodeji and Okorafor (2014) who conducted a study to assess the impact and input of various skills acquisition in Yaba and Akoka environs in Lagos, Nigeria. Ajiboye, Aromolaran, Ayodeji and Okorafor found that Skills acquisition: reduced joblessness; poverty; positively influenced society; enhanced self-reliance/independence and self-employment; engendered positive attitude for work; reduces rate of crime; enhances knowledge acquisition; develops entrepreneurship and self-esteem. On the other hand, finding by Ajiboye, Aromolaran, Ayodeji and Okorafor negates the findings for the male beneficiaries of computer skill development programme since it was found in the present study that computer skill development programme lowly influenced male beneficiaries in terms of community development.

Original Article

4.3.4 Interpersonal Treatment Skills Development Programme and Community Development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Research question four sought to find out the extent interpersonal treatment skills development programme influence community development in Rivers South West Senatorial District of Rivers state. The result from the analysis reveals that both the female and male beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme agree that to a high extent, health workers could now listen to them very well; they no longer depend on traditional medicine; they were no longer ashamed of telling the health worker everything about my health challenges; they were not scared of vaccine; they could conveniently go on medical check-up on regular bases; they now had understanding of the importance of hygiene practices to healthy living.

The result of hypothesis four shows that there was no significant difference in the mean response of the female and male beneficiaries of the human development programme regarding the influence of interpersonal treatment skills development programme on community development. This implies that both male and female beneficiaries of the human resources developments programme agree that the programmeresulted in the development of their communities to a low extent.

This result is in agreement with the finding of Eze (2013) who conducted a study to investigate the role of women in community development in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State. Eze found that economic capacities of women play significant impact on their participation and contributions to development of communities in Nsukka. It follows that beneficiaries of the human development programme got their capacities enhanced through interpersonal treatment skills development programme and as such contributed to the development of their communities. When they are able to discuss the health problems and issues freely with health personnel, they get solutions to such problem. Sequel to this, they live healthy to contribute to the development of their communities.

5.1 Summary of the Study

The research study investigates the influence of human resource development programmes in community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers State. To determine the influence of Computer skills development programme in community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. To examine the influence of Conflict resolution management skills development programme in community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. To investigate the influence of Rural agricultural skills development programme in community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state. To identify the influence of Interpersonal treatment skills development programme in community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers state.

To achieve these objectives, the study set some technical research questions and hypothesis as stated in chapter one. While chapter two of this study contains detailed view of related literature under the following sub-headings: Theoretical framework, Conceptual framework, Empirical review of related literature, and Summary of related literature review. In chapter three, deals with detail methodology on the step-by-step approach to how the results was examined. However, to be specific the structured questionnaires were analyzed using the descriptive statistics and t-test statistic for the hypotheses with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 22. While the Null Hypothesis formulated for the study was set at 0.05 alpha level of significance. And chapter four

Original Article

focused on presentation, data analysis, and discussion of findings. This was done through an in-depth analysis of the structured questionnaires under the concept of both descriptive and t-test statistics under the use of descriptive statistics, a standard mean value was set at 2.50 bench mark for acceptance, while any of the mean score below 2.50 were rejected.

Similarly, the hypotheses for the study were tested using the t-test statistic at the standard t-critical value of 1.96 as a basis for comparison. This was considered as the basis to enhance the Business and certainty in our decision. Also, discussions of findings were very critical to the study. This is because the results of the findings were compared with what other authorities in this area have done before now. This was done in a way to fine tune an appropriate solution to existing problem in the area of community development.

The finding of the study reveal that human resource development programmes have directly influenced community development, to a high extent through the knowledge gained and the skill acquired in computer management skill development and rural agricultural management skill among the female folks while low extent was recorded in conflict resolution management skill and interpersonal treatment management skill in both the female and male counterparts. Findings further indicates that training programme will make a lots of influence if the male folks are actively involved in the human resource development programmes which are one of the most easiest and assured means of empowerment towards building human capacity for both community and national development.

5.2 Conclusion

From the findings, it is concluded that the influence of human resource development programmes in community development in Rivers SouthWest Senatorial District of Rivers State cannot be over emphasize or neglected at all. As beneficiaries especially the female had actively participated in community development programmes have change in their economic status, provide enough food for their families and as such their children has return to school for those who stopped due to financial difficulties, no more case of mal-nourishment as such many families are healthy and happy and there is also relative calmness in this senatorial districts. Participates of these programmes can presently identified felt needs and also training others in their communities. But the major force (male) are slacking in the programmes one would have wondered what would have become of the region if male are part of the programme which calls for an urgent attention of the planners and co-ordinators of human resources development programmes.

5.3 Recommendations

In the light of these findings, the following recommendations are articulated:

1. Human resources development programmes should be fun, less stress and simple to the understanding of the target groups; this is because lack of interest in participating in the computer skill development programme among the male folks may due to the nature of the programme, attitudes of the facilitators and lack of fund for a start-up small scale business at the end of the training programme. This study therefore recommended for proper timing of the programme, the target groups and provision of incentive to the beneficiaries especially the male counterparts. This is because the more the male participates in these programmes, the issue of un-rest, crime and insecurity which of caused are populated by the male will be a thing of the past.

Original Article

2. The low participation of male and female folks into conflict resolution management skills Programmes is due to non-implementation of promises by the organisers of the Programmes. The issue of conflict resolution management should go beyond negotiation and promises; rather the root of the problem should be of major focus and then seek means of providing solution to them.

3. The agricultural sector has machines and farm implements that can be handle by male of which if they are train on how to move them and are employment to drive these machines after the training period, it will motivate them in attending this the training programmes in an addition to that, rural farmer should be giving credit loans and some farm implements as a way of motivating and enhancing their interest and commitments in farming activities towards food production

4. The issue of health should go beyond public awareness or training, this is because the rural people don't always have access to drugs and other health facilities, as such, the coordinators of these programmes should endeavour to offer solution to some minor health problems to the trainees during the training programmes. The health workers should endeavor to revisit the area for effective felt-back and result effectiveness; as such intensive and effective health education is necessary and to be reinforced in order to eliminate and control diseases: like malaria, typhoid etc, more so, Nigerian health policy makers should give priority attention to the training of more rural health workers.

REFERENCES

- Abass, I. M. (2010). Poverty and rural–urban habitats in Nigeria. *Journal of Sociology, Psychology and Anthropology*, 2(2), 113–136.
- Abiodun, A. J. (2010). Patients' satisfaction with quality attributes of primary health care services in Nigeria. *Journal of Health Management*, 12(1), 39–54.
- Abolfazl, M. R., & Behbood, V. T. (2015). Explaining the role of information technology in human resource development. *International Journal of Economy, Management and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 43–51.
- Adeyemo, D. O. (2009). Local government and health care delivery in Nigeria. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 18(2), 149–160.
- Akdere, M. (2005). Integration of the fields of adult education and human resource development: Addressing the workplace challenges. *Proceedings of the 24th Annual Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, and Community Education*, Milwaukee, WI.
- Albert, I. O. (2010). Concepts and methods in peace and conflict studies. In C. Bassey & O. Oshita (Eds.), *Conflict resolution, identity crisis and development in Africa* (pp. 3–18). Lagos, Nigeria: Malthos Press.
- AlYahya, M. S., Norsiah, B. M., & Alharbi, M. A. (2013). Review of theory of human resources development training (learning) participation. In *Proceedings of the WEI International Academic Conference* (pp. 85–92). Antalya, Turkey: West East Institute.

Original Article

- Apple Computer Inc. (2002). *The impact of technology on student achievement: A summary of research findings on technology's impact in the classroom*. <https://www.apple.com/education/research/>
- Armstrong, M. (2015). *A handbook of human resource management practice* (7th ed.). London, UK: Kogan Page.
- Asadullah, A. I., Mohammad, N., Shah, M., & Muhammad, N. (2011). Does human resource development contribute to community development? *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture*, 27(1), 147–152.
- Aworemi, J. R., Abdul-Azeez, I. A., & Opoola, N. A. (2011). An appraisal of the factors influencing rural–urban migration in some selected local government areas of Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4(3), 136–141.
- Dukes, E. F. (2010). *Resolving public conflict: Transforming community and governance*. New York, NY: Manchester University Press.
- Ewuzie, R. (2012). *Change in adult education in Nigeria*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Eze, L. U. (2013). The role of women in community development in Nsukka local government: Challenges and prospects [Master's thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka].
- Gavrileseu, C. C. (2010). *Economic and ecological management of soil resources*. Bucharest, Romania: Romanian Academy Publishing House.
- Ghorbanizadeh, V. (2013). Meta-analysis of factors affecting adoption of information technology in Iran. *Management Research in Iran*, 17(2), 49–57.
- Godongs, S. (2007). Mediation and the mediation process. In C. Bassey & O. Oshita (Eds.), *Conflict resolution, identity crisis and development in Africa* (pp. 130–144). Lagos, Nigeria: Malthos Press.
- Grabe, M., & Grabe, C. (2004). *Integrating technology for meaningful learning*. New York, NY: TopTen.
- Ibe-Bassey, G. S. (2011, September 19–23). Human capacity building for ICT integration in teacher education in Nigeria. Paper presented at the Nigeria Association for Educational Media and Technology International Conference, Imo State University, Owerri.
- Ibok, E. E. (2014a). The role of ministry of rural development in the promotion of community development in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Developing Country Studies*, 4(10), 79–84.
- Ibok, E. E. (2014b). An implementation of primary health care service in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria: An appraisal. *Scientific Research Journal*, 1(4), 60–63.

Original Article

- Ibok, E. E., & Ibanga, S. E. (2015). The impact of human capital development and economic empowerment on the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *European Centre for Research Training and Development UK Journal*, 2(3), 37–44.
- Igbo, R. O. (2008). Contemporary adult education: An inclusive approach. *NCAEP Book of Readings*, 3(1), 132–172.
- Ihejirika, J. C. (2007). *Fundamentals of adult education and community development*. Port Harcourt, Nigeria: Abagab Associates.
- Ihejirika, J. C. (2015). *Adult and non-formal education practice in Nigeria*. Port Harcourt, Nigeria: Abigah Associates Ltd.
- Ihejirika, J. C., & Onyenemezu, M. (2012). Adult education and development of manpower resources in Nigeria. *Department of Adult & Non-Formal Education, University of Port Harcourt*.
- Ikegwu, E. M., Ajiboye, Y. O., Aromolaran, A. D., Ayodeji, A. A., & Okorafor, U. (2014). Human empowerment through skills acquisition: Issues, impacts and consequences—A non-parametric view. *Journal of Poverty, Investment and Development*, 5, 94–101.
- Iwu, A. O. (2005). ICT competencies perceived as required by mathematics lecturers in colleges of education in South-East Zone of Nigeria [Doctoral dissertation, Imo State University, Owerri].
- Iwu, A. O. (2012, May). Roadblocks to integrating ICT in Nigerian schools. Paper presented at the National Conference of the School of Education, Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria.
- Iwu, F. (2008). Inequalities in health care in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Health Policy and Planning*, 3(2), 159–160.
- Keep, E., & Mayhew, K. (2009). The assessment, knowledge, skills, and competitiveness. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 15(1), 1–15.
- Kobani, D. (2014). Economic empowerment programmes and women participation in community development in Rivers State: A study of the Empowerment Support Initiative (ESI). *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(16), 14–20.
- Kobani, D., & Alozie, K. (2015). *Essentials of community development in Nigeria*. Owerri, Nigeria: Beauty Konzept.
- Kobani, D., & Alozie, K. (2016). *Adult education: Principles and practice*. Owerri, Nigeria: Beauty Konzept.

Original Article

Kuyoro, S. O., Awodele, O. O., & Okolie, S. (2012). ICT: An effective tool in human development. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(7), 40–52.

Luthans, F., Avolio, B. J., & Peterson, S. J. (2010). The development and performance impact of psychological capital. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 21(1), 41–67.

Mahroum, S. (2007). Assessing human resources for science and technology: The 3Ds framework. *Science and Public Policy*, 34(7), 489–499.

Malik, K. (2014). *Human development report 2014*. New York, NY: United Nations Development Programme.

Mba, O., Agwu, I., & Ogiriki, T. (2014). Management and sustainability. *Canadian Center of Science and Education Journal*, 4(4), 11–20.